

**AN ALERT SYSTEM TO MONITOR THE FLUID LEVEL IN A FAILED VALVE SYSTEM OF
A SUCTION MACHINE**

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CERTIFICATION

I hereby declare that this project work (“ AN ALERT SYSTEM TO MONITOR THE FLUID LEVEL IN A FAILED VALVE SYSTEM OF A SUCTION MACHINE”) is the result of my original piece of research work conducted between January/2023 and October/2023 under the supervision of Mr. Seidu Abdullah of the department of science, Al-Azhariya senior high school. In instances where references of other works have been cited, full acknowledgment has been given. This work has never been submitted in whole or in part in any institution for any award(s)

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to the Most High God, who gave us his grace and saw us through our stay in Amity University and also my loving parent; Mr & Mrs. Iddrisu, and my project supervisor Mr.Seidu Abdullah

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ABSTRACT

A suction machine, also known as an aspirator, is a type of medical device that is primarily used for removing obstructions — like mucus, saliva, blood, or secretions — from a person's airway. When an individual is unable to clear secretions due to a lack of consciousness or an ongoing medical procedure, suction machines help them breathe by maintaining a clear airway. Users of suction machine which does not have stop cork are faced with the challenge of monitoring the waste collecting jar of the suction machine. As users operate the suction machine, their interest is focused on the patient therefore losing focus on the level of fluid collected in the jar. It is therefore important to design and develop system to monitor the collecting jar of the suction machine. The system was made by integrating various components such as resistors, LED, Arduino nano, crow-tail sensor, buzzer, Diode, capacitor, printed circuit board. C++ programming language was embedded in the system to configure the device. The crow-tail sensor was able to detect the level of fluid in the collecting using the pre-determine threshold given.

In this manner. It is possible to avoid or prevent the flow of fluid back into suction machine without a cork.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

The human body is made up of fluids of various viscosity. Such body fluids are blood, mucus, saliva and secretion. These body fluids have the tendency to obstruct the airway of a person. Whenever these fluid block the airway of a person, there is a need to clear such fluids from the airway. During surgical procedures, such fluids may also interfere on the area of interest. As it is, the fluid must be cleared from the area of interest. In order to remove such fluids obstructing the airways, the suction machine is used. When an unconscious person is unable to clear secretion or during medical procedures, the suction machine aid the breathing of the person by maintaining a cleared airway. In practical sense, suction machine is used as an integral part of treating patient with complete or partial obstructed airway. So the suction machine plays important role in treating patients and during surgical procedures.

As important as the suction machine maybe, it comes with its own challenges during usage. The unwanted fluid that is sucked out of the patients is collected into the waste collecting jar. In the process of using the suction machine, the operator's focus is concentrated on the patient and might not be monitoring the waste collection jar. When the waste collecting jar get filled with the fluid and the jar is not emptied, it becomes a challenge. When the waste collecting jar get filled, back flow of the fluid into the suction machine occurs. The flow of fluid from the waste collecting jar into the suction machine causes the device to abruptly stop. Abrupt stop of the suction machine may put the patient's life in danger. The delay in servicing the suction machine whiles the patient waits might cause the death of the patient.

This proposed work is to come up with a simple system installed on the suction machine to monitor the fluid level of the waste collecting jar. The system will prompt the user as to empty the waste collecting jar base on a predetermined threshold of fluid level.

1.2 AIM

To develop a simple monitoring system to prompt the user of suction machine to empty the waste collecting jar.

This system will help to prevent the flow of waste fluid into the suction machine.

1.3 OBJECTIVE

- To develop a simple and cheap monitoring system for waste collecting jar of a suction machine.
- To prevent flow back of collected body fluid from patient into the suction machine.
- To use electronic component such as buzzer to prompt the user of the suction machine

1.4 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Stop corks that are responsible for preventing the back flow of fluid sucked into the suction machine easily get misplaced. Some of the suction machine also comes without a stop cork. The stop cork is not in the open market for purchasing. The fact that the stop cork is misplaced or unavailable does not mean those machine would not be used. Users of suction machine are faced with the challenge of monitoring the waste collecting jar of the suction machine. As users operate the suction machine, their interest is focused on the patient therefore making loss focus on the level of fluid collected in the jar. This create problem if the collecting jar overfilled and allow fluid to run into the suction machine. The suction machine is brought to a sodden stop and puts the life of the patient in danger.

1.5 JUSTIFICATION

This study will be relevant in helping users of suction machine to monitor the level of collected waste fluid in the waste collecting jar. The outcome of this project will contribute to advancing new technology in manufacturing of suction machine.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 SUCTION MACHINE AND FLUID WASTE MANAGEMENT

The purpose of medical suction is to clear body fluids from the airway and also to get rid of unwanted fluid from the targeted area during surgery. The fluid is collected must be managed such that it doesn't become grounds for spreading infections. By application of technology in the field of medicine, medical suction is achieved but without a pocket of risk to the patient. Risks such as machine failure, infection transmission and excessive negative pressure. Medical suction machine is critical in helping of difficult delivery of new born and aids in resuscitating of critically ill patients. All these produce fluid which contains highly infectious substances. If the fluid is not managed properly, it may pose threats to the patient. World Health Organisation (WHO) stated that the improper management of medical fluid waste can put the patient, staff and community members at risk of infection, toxicity and environmental damage or contamination Chartier Y, et al (2014).

2.2 RELATED ARTICLES

Chun and Zohdy, (2017) in their work 'Medical Suction and Fluid Waste Management', it established the five general causes of adverse events associated with medical suction and the management and disposal of fluid waste. The five general causes are as follows

- a. Human error.
- b. Negative pressure.
- c. Infection related to device use.
- d. Infection related to fluid waste.
- e. Ineffective suction or mechanical/electrical dysfunction.

The study concluded that medical suctioning and fluid collection activities in the healthcare facility is ubiquitous. Technological advancement increases the complexity of medical procedures hence increasing risk to patients, healthcare professionals and the environment.

Khimani, et al (2015) a study carried out on ‘Practices of Tracheal Suctioning Techniques Among Healthcare Professionals’. The study focused on the phases or processes that nurses go through to perform a safe tracheal suction. The three phases that were established spelt out what the healthcare professionals are to do in each phase. The phases include the pre suctioning phase, the suctioning phase and the post suctioning.

The research work concluded that tracheal suctioning is a major and important aspect of keeping the airway cleared of fluid. As important as this care or procedure is, it associated with risk factors. Due to these risk factors, it is important for healthcare professional to follow a proven laid down guidelines to prevent complications and improve safety.

Calkins, et al (2002) conducted a study to evaluate the use of portable and manual suction machine in pre-hospital combat casualty care. They worked on three commercially available devices. Four different devices were used. Two prototype, a syringe and a modified suction device. They concluded that all were able to create negative pressure and therefore able to create suctioning. The shortfall was that the flow

rate couldn't be measured and controlled. In all, they were able to identify one device that was superior to the others by weight, size and performance.

Fig. 1 Syringe

Vandenberg, et al (1998), the work focused on the tip diameter and tubing used during suctioning. It was noticed that Hagen - Poiseuille equation strongly favours larger diameter. They raise concern however on the commonly used Yankaeur suction tip as not being design for precision suctioning during surgeries and not for rapid evacuation of large quantity of obscuring fluids. In other works they studied the suction of various fluids simulating vomitus from some volunteers. Fluid evacuation from large bore was ten times faster than the standard Yankaeur (small) tip. Larger diameter tip does not only increase flow rate but it also reduce clogging.

Carroll (2003) did some work to guide the clinician on selecting the appropriate negative pressure for specific suctioning. The guidelines for airway suctioning suggests 50 to 100 mm Hg is recommended for infant whiles 80 to 120 mmHg is the recommended for children. The recommendation for adult is 100 to 150 mm Hg

Makama JG, et al (2010) established in their work that the vacuum effect of surgical suction tip can induce significant artifactual alteration in the connective tissue which are remove for diagnostic or therapeutic purposes. When a vacuum draws air into the connective tissue artifact occurs.

Priya, et al (2017) in their work concluded that military testing of suction device during combat casualty care makes reference to two sources. The method they use are not standardised and each source focus on different subset of testing putting into account mechanical, environmental and electrical.

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 MATERIALS / COMPONENTS.

The materials which were used for this project was selected based on the following factors: cost, easy to integrate, bio-compatibility. The main idea is to minimize cost as well as ensuring that the functionality of the device is not compromised.

Below is the various list of components used;

S/N	COMMENTS	SPECIFICATION	QUANTITY
1	Crowtail sensor	3 – 6 v dc	1
2	Arduino Nano	12 v dc	1
3	Capacitor		2
4	Resistor		2
5	LED		1
6	Diode		2
7	Buzzer		1

3.1.1 Crow-tail sensor

Crow-tail sensor is a magnetic switch based on an encapsulated dry reed switch MKA14103. MKA14103 is a single pole, single throw (SPST) type having a normally open ruthenium contact. The sensor is a double – ended type which can be used to turn on and off a circuit. The sensor switches on in the presence of load.

3.1.2 Arduino Nano

Fig. 2 Arduino Nano

Arduino Nano is a microcontroller board based on ATmega328. The Arduino Nano is a breadboard friendly board which is made up of series of digital, analog inputs and outputs. The board is able to convert analog signals to digital signals which is then given to an output of a choice. It has 14 digital input / output terminals of which 4 can be used as output and 8 analog input. It also have 16MHz (clock speed) ceramic resonator and a Mini - B USB port connector for uploading the programme language. Unlike Arduino Uno, Arduino Nano lacks DC power jack and works with Mini - B USB instead of the standard USB. It have an option for battery for the source of power. The source is automatically selected. The operating voltage is 5 – 12vdc. In order to get the

controller working, programs needs to be assigned to the ATMEGA328P FLASH memory. After this is done, the controller is then able to execute the code or information after which it provides appropriate responses.

3.1.3 Capacitor

Fig. 3 Capacitor

A capacitor is a component that stores electrical energy or charge when supply with voltage. The stored up energy is used to keep a smooth or steady flow of voltage in the circuit. The capacitor also filters off possible ripples in the circuit. The capacitor is a passive component with two terminal. The effect of capacitor is referred

to as capacitance. It consists of two conductors that are separated by a non-conductive region. The non-conductive region can either be a vacuum or an electric insulator material known as a dielectric.

3.1.4 Resistor

Resistor is a semiconductor component which is used to oppose the flow of electrical current within a circuit. A resistor can either be a fixed or variable in nature. A fixed resistor is the type in which its resistance value is specified and cannot be regulated. A variable resistor is the one which resistance value can be changed. In other ways, the resistor can be used to regulate signals.

Fig 5 Resistor

3.1.5 LED

A light Emitting Diode (LED) is a component that emits light when current flows through it. The light emitting diode emits its light when it is forward biased. When a voltage is applied across the junction to make it forward biased, current flows as in the case of any PN junction.

Fig.6 LED

3.1.6 Diode

As simple as a diode might be, it is one of the most useful semiconductor components in a circuit. Diodes are generally used to control current in one direction. Different types of diodes are used for a wide range of applications. A rectifier diode is used to convert a voltage in an alternative current state to a direct current state. Signal diodes are used in processing signals in an electronic circuit such as obtaining video and audio signals from a transmitted radio frequency. Other types of diodes are Zener diodes and light-emitting diodes.

Fig. 7 Diode

3.1.7 Buzzer

Fig. 8 Buzzer

The buzzer is a device use for audio signals. It convert audio signals into sound signals. It is a active component which will sound or buzz if provided with a steady 5v dc. It sound on it own with a predefined frequency of 2300 Hz.

3.2 METHODOLOGY

This comprises of the various steps taken in achieving a complete system. The step by step procedures in completing a functional device. Testing of the selected components, designing, building and finally, its implementation.

3.3.1 BLOCK DIAGRAM

Fig. 9 Block diagram

The fig..... represents the block diagram of the system. The entire system is powered by the power supply unit. The power supply unit basically pick an AC voltage and convert it to a DC voltage. The power supply unit starts the system. The sensor is basically made up of a very flexible push switch which allows for a system to switch on and off in the presence of a load. So when body fluid collected in the collecting jar fills up, the sensor will detect it as a load and then triggers the system to switch on. The signal picked up by the sensor must be conditioned for the next stage. In conditioning a signal, processes such as signal filtration and signal amplification take place. After the signal is conditioned, the signal must be converted to the right form for the microcontroller to be able to read. The initial signal is in analog state which needs to be converted into a digital state. That is the work of the ADC unit. Now the converted signal is given to the microcontroller. Based on the signal given to the microcontroller, the system it switch on or off. If the system is switched off, no alarm will be sounded. This means the fluid in the collecting jar is not full up. If the system switches on, alarm will be sounded which implies that the fluid level in the collecting jar is getting full up. The buzzer is responsible for sounding the alarm.

FLOW CHART

Fig.10 Flow chart

The flow chart as shown in Fig..... Shows how the system operates. As the system starts, there is a general initialization that triggers the water level sensor to initiate. The sensor first of all detects the presence of fluid in the collecting jar. The fluid level sensor goes ahead to measure the level of fluid present in the collecting jar and compares it to the predetermined fluid level. The system compares the measured fluid level to the predetermined fluid level, if the measured fluid level is lower than the predetermined fluid level, then the process starts again from sensor initialization stage. The entire process begins from the sensor initialization stage and the process is repeated until when the measured fluid level exceeds that of the predetermined fluid level. At this stage, the system starts to buzz to give a warning to the user in order for the fluid collecting jar to be emptied.

3.3.3 CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

The Arduino Nano is the central component which coordinates the operation of the system. It has a barrel jack and a USB port through which it receives power from an external source to operate. It has a recommended operating voltage of 7-12V. The crow tail sensor which is a switch is connected to the Arduino Nano. The circuit which is controlled by the crow tail sensor is an open one. When fluid enters the collecting jar and it is detected by the sensor by contact, the sensor response by making the circuit close. The closed circuit now allows voltage to flow through the system into the Arduino Nano board. The closed circuit allows flow of millivolts to the transistor which acts as a switch. Electrical currents from the transistor switches on the buzzer to sound alarm. When the buzzer sounds alarm, it means that fluid in the collecting jar have reached its level limit and therefore the fluid must be emptied from the collecting jar.

Fig.11 Circuit Diagram

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter deals with the outcome of the design and construction of the device and the discussions related to how it works.

4.2 RESULTS

All the various components were connected in such a way that they performed their functions as a unit. The following tests were carried out.

4.2.1 TESTING WHETHER THE SYSTEM DETECTS FLUID AND ABLE TO SWITCH

The system was put to test to determine whether it is able to detect the level of fluid and switch to sound alarm. The designed system was installed onto a suction machine. The fluid collecting jar of the suction machine did not have a stop cork that is responsible for preventing the back flow of waste fluid collected into the waste collecting jar. The crow tail sensor was installed in the fluid collecting jar by hanging it at the desired level and the other part of the system installed on the suction machine. The system is supplied with the required voltage and the suction machine is switched on to run. Fluid is collected into the jar. The system was monitored and observations made. This test was conducted three times to be sure of how effective and efficient the system is.

4.2.2 OBSERVATION

It was observed that when fluid enters the collecting jar without having any contact with the crow tail sensor, the monitoring system is not activated. The crow tail sensor is installed by hanging it to the desired level in the fluid collecting jar. As the fluid is collected in the jar and the content of the jar is raising up. The fluid gets to the required level where the crow tail sensor is installed. As the fluid touched the crow tail sensor, the circuit closes thereby switching the buzzer to sound the alarm.

4.3 EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION

We set off to design a system which should be able to detect the presence of fluid in a jar, measure the level of the fluid and be able to sound alarm when the fluid exceeds the desired level. From the above test and results, we have observed that the system is able to achieve what we set out to do. At the presence of fluid in the collecting jar, the system does not sound an alarm. This is due to the fact that the crow tail sensor have not yet come into contact with the fluid. When the fluid keep rising and touches the crow tail sensor which is installed at the desired fluid level in the collecting jar, the crow tail sensor detects the fluid as a weight and quickly closes the circuit. The closed circuit compels the crow tail sensor to switch on which intends allow voltage to flow from the Arduino Nano board to the transistor. The transistor also switches on to allow electrical current to flow unto the buzzer and therefore causing the buzzer to sound alarm. The alarm is persistent until the collecting jar is emptied of the fluid. The alarm cannot be stopped until there is no fluid in the collecting jar.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 CONCLUSION

The use of suction in our daily operations in delivery of healthcare cannot be over emphasised. The suction machine is one important device used in giving treatment to clients in the hospital. As important as the suction machine maybe, it comes with its own challenges during usage. The unwanted fluid that is sucked out of the patients is collected into the waste collecting jar. In the process of using the suction machine, the operator's focus is concentrated on the patient and might not be monitoring the waste collection jar. When the waste collecting jar get filled with the fluid and the jar is not emptied, it becomes a challenge as the collected waste fluid can flow back into the suction machine. The flow of fluid from the waste collecting jar into the suction machine causes the device to abruptly stop. Abrupt stop of the suction machine may put the patient's life in danger. The need to monitor the level of the content in the waste collecting jar becomes necessary to prevent the abrupt stoppage of the machine.

The designed system is able to measure the fluid level in the collecting jar. When the fluid exceeds the pre-set level of the collecting jar, the monitoring system is able to sound alarm. The alarm is persistent until the collecting jar of emptied. The alarm cannot be stopped until the fluid is emptied from the collecting jar.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

Since when the monitoring system sounds the alarm, it is dependent on the user of the suction machine to empty the waste collecting jar, we recommend that with the fast advancement in technology, the monitoring system

can be designed in such a way that upon persistent alarm, it will shut the suction machine down to prevent the back flow of the waste fluid into the system.

5.2 LIMITATION

The following limitations were observed during the testing of the device.

- I. The persistent sounding of the alarm can be disturbing, but this system is limited in such that, system does not have the option to stop the alarm until the waste collecting jar is emptied.
- II. The monitoring system is unable to shut the suction down after persistent sounding of alarm and the user decides to continue using the suction machine instead of emptying the waste collecting jar.

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APPENDIX

```
#include <avr/io.h>

#define F_CPU 16000000

#define BLINK_DELAY_MS 5000

#include <util/delay.h>

int main (void)

{

// Arduino digital pin 3 for input

DDRD = DDRD & 0B11110111;

DDRB = DDRB & 0B00000110; //

while(1) {

// turn buzzer on

if(PORTD & 0B00001000){

PORTB |= 0B110; // _delay_ms(BLINK_DELAY_MS);

// turn buzzer off

PORTB &= ~ 0B110; // _delay_ms(BLINK_DELAY_MS);

}

}

}
```

